

IS THE EXPORT-LED GROWTH HYPOTHESIS VALID FOR DEVELOPING COUNTRIES? A CASE STUDY OF BANGLADESH

Md. Mahmudul Hassan*

ABSTRACT

The association between exports and growth is often attributed to the possible positive externalities for the domestic economy arising from participation in world markets. The purpose of this paper is to evaluate whether export revenues can lead to significant and positive economic growth in a country. The paper uses time series econometric analysis to test the causal relationship between exports and economic growth. The results indicate that export revenues have led to positive and significant economic growth in Bangladesh. The paper concludes that the export oriented i.e. outward looking approach led to GDP growth in Bangladesh economy. In order to increase the reliability of the study; we have employed modern time series econometric techniques and procedures.

Keywords: *Export-led growth hypothesis (ELGH); economic growth; cointegration; Granger Causality*

INTRODUCTION

The export-led growth hypothesis (ELGH) postulates that export expansion is one of the main determinants of growth. It holds that the overall growth of countries can be generated not only by increasing the amounts of labour and capital within the economy, but also by expanding exports. According to its advocates, exports can perform as an “engine of growth”. The ELG paradigm has received a lot of attention following the highly successful East Asian (Taiwan, Hong Kong, Singapore and Korea, the Four Asian Tigers) export-led growth strategy during the 1970s and 1980s. The hypothesis implies not only that exports and economic growth are highly correlated, but that the former unidirectionally causes the latter. There has been a large-scale swing towards the ELG strategy in latest years. There are different reasons behind this. The benefits of the ELG strategy have led, not only to the implementation of this strategy by many countries, but also to a growing of many studies to test the pragmatic legitimacy of the hypothesis (see Greenaway and Sapsford, 1994, Shan and Sun, 1998). Nonetheless, there are silent questions as to whether the ELG strategy will also be favorable to the small economies of a country like Bangladesh. This question will be the focus of this paper. Specifically, the objective

* Lecturer, Department of Economics, School of Social Science, Asian University of Bangladesh, Bangladesh, E-mail: mhsnju@gmail.com

of this paper is to assess whether export revenues can lead to significant and positive economic growth in BD economy. To achieve this, the paper uses time series econometric analysis to test the causal relationship between exports and economic growth. This paper will provide some useful insights to policy makers in Bangladesh.

The objective of this paper is twofold. First, examine whether indeed there is a causal relationship between exports and economic growth. Second, determine the direction of this causation.

The article is arranged as follows: Following the introductory part Section 2 discusses the contribution of exports to Botswana's economic growth as shown by statistical evidence and econometric evidence. Section 3 is a summary of conclusions and policy recommendations.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE

The existing literature on seeking the correlation between export and output concentrates mostly on causality from exports to output. Yet, there are logical arguments for reverse causality from output to exports too. Among the early studies, Michaely (1977), Chow (1987), Darrat (1987), Erfani (1999), Abual-Foul (2004) and Awokuse (2004) have provided evidence in support of export-led growth hypothesis for various developing countries. Erfani (1999) examined the causal relationship between economic performance and exports over the period of 1965 to 1995 for several developing countries in Asia and Latin America. The result showed the significant positive relationship between export and economic growth. This study also provides the evidence about the hypothesis that exports lead to higher output.

But the results of the recent studies show weak causation or almost no relation between export and economic growth. Mah (2005) studied the long-run causality between export and growth which indicated that export expansion is insufficient to explain the patterns of economic growth. The study by Tang (2006) showed no long run relationship among export, imports and real GDP.

Jordaan (2007) analyzed the hypothesis of growth led by export which revealed that exports Granger cause GDP. By using panel data analysis Pazim (2009) tested the validity of export-led growth hypothesis in three countries and concluded that there is no significant relationship between the size on national income and amount of export while the panel co-integration test indicates that there is no equilibrium relationship between the export and economic growth for these countries.

DATA SOURCES, MEASUREMENT, AND DESCRIPTION

The analysis is based on annual time series data on exports value and real GDP in local currency units (in billion taka). The data set is annual, spanning 1973/74 through 2009/10. The data on exports was collected from Export Promotion Bureau and the data of real GDP was taken from different year's publication of BBS, Statistical Year Book, and Economic Review. To test if the series are non-stationary or contain a unit root, we focus on the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) test simultaneously. We have used EViews as statistical software package.

ECONOMETRICS METHODOLOGY

To see the effect of export growth on GDP and at the same time the effect of GDP growth on export we have run the following two regressions simultaneously adjusting the stationarity characteristics of the considered variables:

$$\Delta^2 RGDP = a + b EXP + u \quad (1)$$

$$EXP = c + d \Delta^2 RGDP + v \quad (2)$$

Where a and c are the intercept terms,

b and d are coefficients, u and v are the white noise error terms in equation [1] and [2] respectively.

Table 1
Regression Result

variables	Dependent variable	Constant	$bEXP$	$d\Delta^2 RGDP$	R-Sq	R-Sq(adj)
EQ[1]	$\Delta^2 RGDP$	-11462 (-1.07)**	124 (3.06)*	-	22.7%	20.3%
EQ[2]	EXP	146 (4.43)*	-	0.00182 (3.06)*	22.7%	20.3%

Notes: Dependent variable is inflation ($\Delta^2\pi$). t-Statistics are displayed in brackets.

* denotes rejection of H_0 at 1%, 5% and 10% level: the coefficient is zero

Source: Authors' own calculation.

All the estimated coefficients have expected sign. The coefficient of export is highly correlated with the RGDP. That is export growth highly contributes to economic growth of the country. One unit increase in the export growth rate is associated with 124 unit of increase in economic growth. Similarly economic growth is positively related to export but not so strongly. Surprisingly both the R-Sq and R-Sq (adj) show small value.

5.1. Unit Root Test

The ADF test is based on the assumption that the residuals are independently and identically distributed. Phillips and Perron (1998) provide an alternative test for the unit roots that is robust to a wide variety of stochastic processes for the disturbance term. The null hypothesis of these tests is that series are non-stationary.

Table 2
Unit Root Test (Non Stationarity)

Variable	ADF (Level)		PP (Level)	
	Intercept	Trend & Intercept	Intercept	Trend & Intercept
RGDP	2.5642 (L=1)**	0.9137(L=1)**	2.9007*	1.2310**
EXP	2.8807 (L=1)*	1.7792 (L=1) **	13.4774**	5.4093**

Notes: (1) Figures within parentheses indicate lag lengths chosen by the Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC). (2) while** denotes rejection of null hypothesis of unit root at the 1%, 5% and 10% level, * denotes rejection of null hypothesis of unit root at 10% level only. The test statistics value of PP test is based on Spectral estimation method-Bartlett Kernel and the Bandwidth is New-West Bandwidth automatic selection by the software itself.

Table 3
Unit Root Test (Stationarity)

Variable	ADF (Level)		PP (Level)	
	Intercept	Trend & Intercept	Intercept	Trend & Intercept
RGDP	-3.0830 (L=1)	0.9952	-4.6537	-4.5513 **
EXP	2.8807(L=1)*	-3.1583 (L=1)	13.4774	5.4093 **

Notes: (1) Figures within parentheses indicate lag lengths chosen by the Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC). (2) while** denotes rejection of null hypothesis of unit root at the 1%, 5% and 10% level, * denotes rejection of null hypothesis of unit root at 10% level only. The test statistics value of PP test is based on Spectral estimation method-Bartlett Kernel and the Bandwidth is New-West Bandwidth automatic selection by the software itself.

Though real GDP (RGDP) shows nonstationarity at level, export (EXP) does not. But taking first difference of RGDP does not show stationary for which we had to take the second difference of RGDP. However, surprisingly the second difference of trend and intercept under ADF test does not show stationarity except the other three cases. Yet our decision to RGDP is integrated of order 2.

5.2. Testing for Cointegration

If individual time series turn out to be non-stationary in their levels (contain stochastic trends), it is possible that stochastic trends are common across series leading to stationary combinations of the levels. For instance, in a bivariate set up, a linear combination of two variables may be stationary even though each variable follows a random walk process. This is known as cointegration. And since the order of integration of the variables is not same we cannot go for cointegration test i.e. checking the long run relationship.

5.3. Test for Granger Causality

Within a vector auto-regression (VAR) framework, the concept of Granger causality is employed to assess whether or not the economy of the country exhibits statistically significant evidence of export-led growth. Granger causality is a technique for determining whether one time series is useful in forecasting another. In a two variable universe, Y_t is said to cause X_t in the Granger sense if the one-step ahead forecast of X_t improves by taking into account the historical values of Y_t . More specifically, tests for Granger causality are based on the following VAR model.

Lags: 1

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Probability
EXP does not Granger Cause RGDP	35	20.4549	7.9E-05
RGDP does not Granger Cause EXP		0.38185	0.54099

Lags: 2

EXP does not Granger Cause RGDP	34	22.1089	1.5E-06
RGDP does not Granger Cause EXP		0.55513	0.57998

Lags: 3

EXP does not Granger Cause RGDP	33	21.5105	3.2E-07
RGDP does not Granger Cause EXP		0.55609	0.64869

Lags: 4			
EXP does not Granger Cause RGDP	32	17.5699	9.8E-07
RGDP does not Granger Cause EXP		0.33564	0.85110
Lags: 5			
EXP does not Granger Cause RGDP	31	13.8388	6.5E-06
RGDP does not Granger Cause EXP		5.48095	0.00246
Lags: 6			
EXP does not Granger Cause RGDP	30	17.8947	1.7E-06
RGDP does not Granger Cause EXP		6.85989	0.00078
Lags: 7			
EXP does not Granger Cause RGDP	29	25.3829	6.4E-07
RGDP does not Granger Cause EXP		6.05949	0.00213
Lags: 8			
EXP does not Granger Cause RGDP	28	17.8493	2.9E-05
RGDP does not Granger Cause EXP		3.57946	0.02702
Lags: 9			
EXP does not Granger Cause RGDP	27	14.9417	0.00043
RGDP does not Granger Cause EXP		5.28352	0.01412

Clearly, we see that in all cases there exists strong causality between the variables when we run the causality from export to RGDP i.e. unidirectional causality from export to real GDP. The number of lags is based on the lowest value of Schwarz Information criterion (SIC).

CONCLUSION

In the theoretical literature there has been greater focus on the decisive role of the export sector as a vehicle to accelerate economic growth. Most economists have argued that opening up of economies is an effective strategy of achieving faster economic growth. It is asserted that export growth emanating from outward oriented economic policies leads to augment GDP growth. In addition, there is potential for reverse causality, i.e. GDP growth leads to export growth. These issues are still unsettled, and there is paradoxical empirical evidence which throw-outs the hypothesis of such relationships between economic and export growth. However, the broad consensus among economists as well as among policy makers is that there is a close symbiotic relationship between GDP growth and export growth.

To summarize, the study confirms that export growth has been instrumental in accelerating economic growth in all the economies.

Reference

- Abual-Foul, B. (2004), Testing the Export-led Growth Hypothesis: Evidence from Jordan, *Applied Economics Letters*, 11, 393–6.
- Awokuse, T. O. (2004), Is the Export-led Growth Hypothesis Valid for Canada?, *Canadian Journal of Economics*, 36, 126–36.
- Chow, P. C. Y. (1987), Causality between Export Growth and Industrial Development: Empirical Evidence from NICs, *Journal of Development Economics*, 26, 55–63.

- Darrat, A. F. (1987), Are Exports an Engine of Growth? Another Look at the Evidence, *Applied Economics*, 19, 277–8.
- Darrat, Ali, (1986), “Trade and Development: The Asian Experience”, *Cato Journal*, Vol. 6.
- Erfani, G. R., (1999), “Export and Economic Growth in Developing Countries”, *International Advances in Economic Research*, Vol. 5.
- Jordaan, A. C. and J. H. Eita, (2007), “Export and Economic Growth in Namibia: A Granger Causality Analysis”, *South African Journal of Economics*, Vol. 75: 3.
- Mah, J. S., (2005), “Export Expansion, Economic Growth and Causality in China”, *Applied Economics Letters*, Vol. 12.
- Mamuna K. A. Al and Nath H. K. Export-led growth in Bangladesh: A Time Series Analysis, *Applied Economics Letters*, 2005, 12, 361–364.
- Michaely, M. (1977), Exports and Growth: An Empirical Investigation, *Journal of Development Economics*, 4, 49–53.
- Pazim, K. H., (2009), “Panel Data Analysis of “Export-led” Growth Hypothesis in BIMF-EAGA Countries, MPRA, paper# 13264.
- Sikder, Faruque M. Omar Export-led Economic Growth in Bangladesh: An Empirical Analysis Economics of Innovation & Growth KTH, Sweden.
- Tang, T. C., (2006), “New Evidence on Export Expansion, Economic Growth and Causality in China”, *Applied Economics Letters*, Vol. 13.